

INFLUENCE OF BRAND AWARENESS ON GROWTH OF MARKET SHARE OF AIRTEL KENYA

Paul Mwaura¹, Robert Mang'ana²

^{1,2} College of Human Resource and Development
Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7774255>

Published Date: 27-March-2023

Abstract: This study sought to understand the influence of brand awareness on growth of market share of airtel Kenya. The research study used descriptive research design while primary data was collected using questionnaires and interviews. Secondary data was collected through analyzing company and industry regulator published reports. Inferential statistics was used to test hypothesis and draw generalized conclusions on the research study. The study targeted a population of 300 customers and subscribers of Airtel Kenya within Nairobi central business district and 50 employees of Airtel Kenya in various customer care shops within the locality. The sample size was limited to 100 subscribers and 34 employees of Airtel Kenya. Data was processed through statistical package for social sciences (SPSS v. 27) while Findings and conclusion were presented in form of tables and figures. The study established a positive and significant relationship between brand awareness ($\beta_1=1.316$, $p\text{-value}=0.001<0.05$). The study recommends that Telecommunication firms and in particular Airtel Kenya, should consistently apply advertisements, sales promotions and publicity to create brand awareness.

Keywords: Brand awareness, Market Share, Airtel Kenya.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Nairobi, a study by Andai (2016) on the influence of brand equity on consumer purchase choices among pay TV subscribers in Nairobi, Kenya revealed that brand equity influenced consumer purchase choices among pay TV subscribers. The findings also revealed that among the brand equity properties, perceived quality had the highest influence on purchase choices, in addition, there was a significant relationship between brand equity properties and purchase choices among pay TV subscribers. Munyau (2017) investigated the role of Customer Based Brand Equity On brand Market Performance in the Banking Service Sector in Kenya. The review inferred that the client based brand value assumes a critical part in generally market brand execution as estimated based on brand mindfulness, brand affiliation, perceived quality and client brand unwaveringness. Consequently the study recommended that service firms and extensionally manufacturing firms should strive to build brand loyalty based not only on customers but also financial and employee brand equity. On her part Asuma (2014) examined the influence of brand equity on the choice of marketing strategies by manufacturers of carbonated drinks in Kenya. The study concluded that brand loyalty leads to increased market share, higher profits and better goodwill among consumers. The study also concluded that to develop a strong brand equity companies have to develop a high level of brand awareness. Wambua (2004) conducted a study on consumer based brand equity and financial performance: a study of the commercial banks in Kenya. The study sought to investigate whether there was a correlation between Consumer Based Brand Equity and Financial Performance in service brands. After examination, the results revealed that consumer based brand equity can yield significant improvement in financial performance of service brands and positively impact return to shareholders. Additionally this improves the brands competitive advantage.

Market share is the percentage of a market (defined in terms of either units or revenue) accounted for by a specific entity (Pfeifer et al. 2006). It is a measure of the consumers' preference for a product over other similar products. A higher market share usually means greater sales, lesser effort to sell more and a strong barrier to entry for other competitors. A higher market share also means that if the market expands, the leader gains more than the others. Market share is both a measure of performance and a measure of competitive strength. Market share makes it easier to get shelf space. It makes it easier to get a consumer who is new to the product category to pay attention to the brand (Vithala et al 1998). Higher market share has a positive benefits such as brand recognition, differentiation, economies of scale and benefits from low costs strategies (Farris, 2010). Marketers need to be able to translate sales targets into market share because this will demonstrate whether forecasts are to be attained by growing with the market or by capturing share from competitors. The latter will almost always be more difficult to achieve. Market share is closely monitored for signs of change in the competitive landscape, and it frequently drives strategic or tactical action (Reibstein et al. 2006).

Market share growth is the ultimate goal of any competitive brand. Every business works hard to increase and protect its market share. This is done by offering superior products and services at competitive prices (Reibstein et al. 2006). Market share is an indicator of how well a firm is doing against its competitors. This metric, supplemented by changes in sales revenue, helps managers evaluate both primary and selective demand in their market. That is, it enables them to judge not only total market growth or decline but also trends in customers' selections among competitors. Generally, sales growth resulting from primary demand (total market growth) is less costly and more profitable than that achieved by capturing share from competitors. Conversely, losses in market share can signal serious long-term problems that require strategic adjustments. Firms with market shares below a certain level may not be viable. Similarly, within a firm's product line, market share trends for individual products are considered early indicators of future opportunities or problems (Farris et al. 2006).

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Brands with high levels of equity are associated with outstanding performance which include premium prices, high market shares, successful expansion into new markets, competitive cost structures and high profitability all contributing to companies' competitive advantage (Keller and Lehmann 2003; Vazquez et al. 2002). Brand equity is significant in assisting consumers to process information, especially when the information is overloaded (Krishan and Hartline, 2001). For firms, growing brand equity is a key objective to be achieved by gaining more favourable associations and feelings of target customers (Christodoulides et al. 2015).

Marketshare of a firm is intuitively expected to be improved as a result of brand equity (Jeon, 2017). This can be done by creating sustainable competitive advantage among the competition. In terms of marketing management, one of the best tools available is the brand (s) (Dunda, 2017). The ways to manage it properly to gain competitive advantage in the market provides an important research area.

Marketshare of a firm is intuitively expected to be improved as a result of brand equity Airtel Kenya and Safaricom have provided the main competition to the industry. Mobile telephony industry in Kenya is characterised by entry barriers upon which new entrants are barred from entering the industry, hence a few firms dominate the industry (Sarigollu, 2014). Kenya's mobile phone industry is in a state of flux. In 2016 alone, the three main players in the industry: Safaricom, Telkom Kenya Ltd. and Airtel Kenya had launched a number of new services for their consumers, moves which exhibit fierce competition in the industry (Kirui & Dunda, 2017). It would therefore, be beneficial for the industry players to understand the underlying structure and the nature, source and strength of competitive forces, hence the need for structural and competitive analysis of the industry (Karobia, 2017).

Empirical studies done in Kenya include a study done by Kiberen, Musiega and Juma (2013) on influence of brand management on Rivalry for Consumers in the Mobile Telecommunication Industry which confirmed rivalry between the mobile telecommunication service providers. The study whose objective was to establish factors that affect consumers purchasing behavior and find out how the consumers benefit from the rivalry did not venture in to brand equity dimensions and therefore offers little knowledge on the subject. Other than concluding that income and employment level determined purchasing behavior and that consumers' benefit from rivalry of service providers, the researchers did not consider brand equity as a determinant to purchase decisions. Agumba et al. (2017) looked at effects of brand awareness on customer retention in the mobile telecommunication industry in Kenya, however this was a case study of Airtel. Although the study investigated one of the four dimensions of brand equity, it limited itself to brand awareness giving

little attention to other factors that determine brand equity. Other Kenyan scholars who have shed light on influence of brand equity in the telecommunication industry investigated individual factors contributing to brand equity but failed to consider brand equity in totality. These include Kibeh (2013) who analysed customer relationship marketing and customer loyalty in telecommunication industry in Kenya. The study examined factors contributing to customer loyalty which is an important factor in brand equity but did not attempt to go further than that. This created a gap in the totality of the subject which needs to be filled. Chepkwony, Langat and Rop (2018) studied the influence of brand equity on financial performance. Although a deliberate effort was employed on influence of brand equity, the only impact examined was on financial performance which cannot be generalized to support market share growth. Therefore, this research seeks to fill the knowledge gap by answering the questions; what is the influence of brand awareness on market share growth of Airtel Kenya.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Brand awareness is the extent to which customers are able to recall or recognize a brand under different conditions (Rossiter & Percy, 1987). The consumer's ability to recognize or recall a brand is central to purchasing decision making. Purchase decision cannot commence unless a consumer is first aware of the brand within a category.

Brand awareness has two components: brand recognition and brand recall. These two components operate in different fundamental ways. Brand recognition entails object recognition while brand recall involves memory retrieval (Farris, Paul, Bendle, Pfeifer, & Reibstein, 2010). Brand recall also known as unaided recall or spontaneous recall refers to the ability of consumers to correctly generate a brand from memory when prompted by a product category (Keller, 1993). Brand recognition also known as aided recall refers to the ability of the consumers to confirm that they have seen or heard of a given brand before (Keller, 2008). It means that consumers can recognize the brand upon presentation either at the point of sale or after viewing its visual packaging (Percy & Rossiter, 1992).

Consumers mostly purchase one of the top three brands in their consideration set. This is known as top-of-mind awareness. Every telecommunication service provider's goal is to increase the probability that consumers will include their brand in their consideration sets. By definition top-of-mind awareness is the first brand that comes to mind when a customer is asked an unprompted question about a category (Farris et al. 2010).

Brand awareness is related to the functions of brand identities in consumers' memory and can be measured by how well the consumers can identify the brand under various conditions (Keller 1993). Given the huge amount of information and brands that consumers are exposed to every day, a brand which enjoys brand awareness to the audience stands a greater chance for consideration in purchase decision. This head start will act as a competitive advantage in maintaining and increasing the market share of the brand (Manternach, 2011). Consequently the confidence and trust in product offering is greatly enhanced as the customer perceived risk and purchase decision process are greatly reduced saving the customer lengthy information costs and product dissonance. On the other hand the company enjoys loyalty and positive advocacy which leads to brand growth in the market share.

Farris and colleagues (2010) have defined market share as "the percentage of a market (defined in terms of either units or revenue) accounted for by a specific entity" (Farris et al. 2010). Market share reflects how marketing expenditures contribute to stakeholders' value. As a measure of marketing productivity, market share is also linked with the overall firm's profitability. It is crucial to establish a positive link between profitability and non-financial marketing measures in order to maintain marketers' credibility and reinforce the importance of the marketing function within a firm. Among different measures of performance, market share is a key indicator of market competitiveness, i.e. how well a firm is doing against its competitors (Buzzell et al., 1975; Farris et al., 2010). Given the ever increasing pressure on marketing executives to account for marketing activities within the firm, examining market share – profitability relationship and strategic value of marketing metrics is of paramount importance to marketing scholars and practitioners. As market share increases, a business is likely to have a higher profit margin, a declining purchases-to-sales ratio, a decline in marketing costs as a percentage of sales, higher quality, and higher priced products (Buzzell et al., 1974).

An empirical study conducted by Holly Hyunjung et al. (2012) on conceptualizing destination brand equity dimensions from a consumer – based brand equity perspective, the empirical results were based on a consumer survey of 326 respondents in Malaysia and was seeking to identify the relational linkages between four principle brand equity dimensions. Using structural equation modelling the study concluded the importance of brand awareness in building

destination brand equity(Hyunjung., Seongseop., Elliot., & Han., 2012). Xuehua Wang & Zhilin Yang (2010) conducted a study on “the effect of brand credibility on consumers’ brand purchase intention in emerging economies: the moderating role of brand awareness and brand image”. The study which focused on China’s automobile industry revealed that brand awareness and brand image are found to positively moderate the relationship between brand credibility and consumers’ brand purchase intention.

A study conducted by Nyagechi (2011) on perception of brand equity of newspapers by media buying agencies in Nairobi, Kenya. Adopted the Aaker (1996) model of brand equity. The study collected data by administering questionnaires to media buying agencies in Nairobi that were identified to have a significant media buying share in 2010 in a report by Synovate. The study revealed that perception of the brand equity elements of the daily newspapers affected the buying behavior of the media buyers as the main findings. Kabura opines in her research on usage of brand equity assets in positioning brands – a case of agrochemical industries based in Nairobi that brand awareness was considered as a key milestone in the competitive agrochemical industry(Kabura, 2002). A study by Munyao (2017) tested the role of customer based brand equity on brand performance in the banking service sector in Kenya.He used a sample of 400 account holder in various banks and 44 branch managers of various banks. The study concluded that relationship between overall brand awareness as a component of customer based brand equity and overall market brand performance was positive and significant.

4. METHODOLOGY

The research study used descriptive research design while primary data was collected using questionnaires and interviews. Secondary data was collected through analyzing company and industry regulator published reports. Inferential statistics was used to test hypothesis and draw generalized conclusions on the research study. The study targeted a population of 300 customers and subscribers of Airtel Kenya within Nairobi central business district and 50 employees of Airtel Kenya in various customer care shops within the locality. The sample size was limited to 100 subscribers and 34 employees of Airtel Kenya. Data was processed through statistical package for social sciences (SPSS v. 27) while Findings and conclusion were presented in form of tables and figures.

5. FINDINGS

The researcher sought to understand if the respondent could easily and quickly identify the Airtel Kenya brand and their level of brand recall. Results of the findings were presented in table 1. In investigating this, seven questions were presented in form of a questionnaire to the respondents in a five point Likert scale ranging from 1(strongly disagree) to 5(strongly agrees). From the analysis of the findings, respondents’ number one choice of telecommunication services showed that 81.6% (M = 4.26, SD =1.048) of the respondent consider Airtel Kenya their first choice in telecommunication services. A whopping 94.9% (M = 4.44, SD = .704) had no difficulty imagining the Airtel brand in their mind, on brand recall 96.9% (M = 4.72, SD = .752) of the respondents could easily recall the Airtel Brand through its corporate colors. 83.6% (M = 4.41, SD = .872) could easily identify the company logo and symbols. On being to date with the latest technology 93.9% (M = 4.57, SD = .647) agreed with the statement. 97.9% considers Airtel Kenya their favorite Telco company (M = 4.69, SD = .706) while Airtel Brand popping to mind when people talk about telecommunication had an 89.8% (M = 4.60, SD = .756) approval.

Table 1: Brand awareness construct

	SD	D	N	A	SA	M	Stdv
Statement:							
Airtel Kenya is the first option that comes into my mind when I need telecommunication services.	4.1	3.1	11.2	26.5	55.1	4.26	1.048
I have no difficulty imagining Airtel Kenya brand in my mind	1.0	1.0	3.1	42.9	52	4.44	.704
The corporate colours of Airtel Kenya are clear in my mind and I can easily identify them.	1.0	0.0	2.0	20.4	76.5	4.72	.752
I can quickly and easily identify the Airtel Kenya logo and symbols.	1.0	2.0	13.3	22.4	61.2	4.41	.872

When I think of telecommunication technology advancement, Airtel Kenya pops in my mind.	1.0	0.0	5.1	29.6	64.3	4.57	.647
Among the industry competitors, Airtel Kenya is my favourite.	0.0	0.0	2.0	26.5	71.4	4.69	.706
When someone speaks about telecommunication, my favourite company comes into mind.	0.0	0.0	9.2	21.4	69.1	4.60	.756

Results from qualitative analysis on ways that brand awareness can be improved, showed that most of the respondents 72%, felt that advertising in mainstream media and social media sites would improve on brand awareness. They also felt that advertisement should be complimented by public relations activities such as corporate social responsibilities projects.

In this section, the results of the hypothesized relationship between brand awareness construct and the overall brand performance (market share growth) are presented and discussed. The Null and Alternative hypothesis are stated as follows:

H₀: Brand awareness has no significant influence on growth of market share of Airtel Kenya.

H_{A1}: Brand awareness has statistically significant influence on growth of market share of Airtel Kenya.

A Pearson's Product Moment Correlation analysis was conducted using average scores of brand awareness constructs (brand recall, brand recognition and overall brand awareness) and brand market performance variables (revenue, customer and employee measures and overall brand market performance).

Table 2; Correlations between Brand Awareness Measures and Brand Market share growth Measures of Airtel Kenya.

		Brand recall	Brand recognition	Brand awareness	Revenue measure	Customer measure	Employee measure
Brand recall	Pearson's r	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)						
	N	98					
Brand recognition	Pearson's r	0.85	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.079					
	N	98					
Brand awareness	Pearson's r	.764**	.638**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000				
	N	98	98	98			
Revenue measure	Pearson's r	.438	.356	.261	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.021	.013	.024			
	N	98	98	98	98		
Customer measure	Pearson's r	.095	.153	.246	-.091	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.037	.045	.033	.037		
	N	98	98	98	98	98	
Employee Measure	Pearson's r	.178**	.069	.257	.182	.273**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.036	.028	.032	.042	.003	
	N	98	98	98	98	98	98
Overall brand performance	Pearson's r	.436*	.182	.479*	.389*	.693**	.527**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.014	.038	.017	.019	.001	.000
	N	98	98	98	98	98	98

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The bivariate correlation analysis from table 2 showed that the relationship between the brand awareness construct of brand recall, brand recognition and brand awareness in relation to the overall brand performance from the perspective of revenue generated, customers' feedback and employee retention had a positive and significant relationship as all the p values were less than 0.05 ($p < .05$) significant level.

The results depicted that customers and prospects who had no difficulties identifying the Airtel brand and had high brand recall from the competing brands, translated to higher revenues to the brand (Airtel Kenya) and reduced the competition risk of losing that customer to a competing brand.

The results of the correlation analysis supported the assertion of the alternative hypothesis (H_{a1}) that Brand awareness has statistically significant influence on growth of market share of Airtel Kenya. In effect the null hypothesis (H_{01}) that stated that brand awareness had no significant influence on growth of market share of Airtel Kenya was not supported by this study and consequently the null hypothesis was dropped in favor of the alternative hypothesis. The study agreed with the study by Huang & Sarigollu (2012) and Baldauf, et al. (2013) whose finding were that there exists a positive relationship between brand awareness and brand market performance leading to securing the market share of the brand or increasing the market share.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In brand awareness examination on its relationship and influence to market share growth, it was deduced in this study to mean the extent to which customers were able to recall and recognize a brand under different conditions (Rossiter, 2009). The customer's ability to recall and recognize a brand was noted in this study to be fundamental in purchase decision making. Buying cannot ensue unless a customer is first cognizant of a product category and a brand within that category. Keller, (2012) noted how brand recall and brand recognition as components of brand awareness operated differently. Brand recall is associated with memory retrieval while brand recognition involves object recognition. Brand awareness is a key indicator of brand's competitive market performance (Cleveland, et al, 2007) and resilient brand awareness can be a predictor of brand accomplishment. Essential tools that marketing firms use to achieve brand awareness include advertising and sales promotion. Amplified exposure to brand advertising raise customer awareness and expedite consumer processing of the included information, by doing this, it improves customers' brand recall and attitude towards the brand (Schmidt, et al, 2015). It was comprehended from this study analysis that brand awareness, with its two main components of brand recall and brand recognition was significant and positively correlated to brand performance influencing market share growth. This conclusion was in tandem with previous studies by Huang and Sarigollu (2012), Kim, et al, (2013) and Younus, et al, (2021) whose results indicated that brand awareness had a positive and significant influence on brand performance leading to competitive edge in market share growth.

Brand awareness, it has been established from the study, is the most important element in making the customer aware of the existence of a brand and or product. A brand stands a chance of being included in the purchase decision consideration, only when the prospect is aware of the existence of that brand. No matter how well the brand is capable of solving the customer needs, if it is unknown to the customer, it will not be considered in solving that particular need. The key elements of brand awareness were noted to be brand recall and brand recognition, brand recall involved memory retrieval while brand recognition involves object recognition through sight and feel. Marketing communication tools such as advertising, sales promotion and word of mouth are key in informing customers and prospects of the existence and importance of the brand. Multiple exposure to the brand through advertisements, sales promotion and positive word of mouth advocacy, aids brand recall in customer's memory, while having a distinct brand image through unique colors, logos and symbols aids in brand recognition. It is recommended that Airtel Kenya should sustain its brand awareness efforts as a long term measure, through the highlighted marketing communication tools to secure and even increase their market share. Brand awareness as opposed to the other three dimensions is initiated by the marketing firm (Airtel Kenya). The rest will be a response to this initiative. It is therefore paramount for Airtel Kenya and other telecom service providers to invest resources for creation of strong brand awareness to its target segment(s), as without brand awareness, it is practically impossible to create brand equity.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aaker. (1991). *Managing Brand Equity: Capitalizing on the value of a brand name*. New York: Free Press.
- [2] Aaker, D. (1996). Measuring Brand Equity Across Products and Markets. *California Management Review*, vol. 38, 102-120.
- [3] Aaker, D. A., & Joachimsthaler, E. (2000). *Brand Leadership*. New York: Free Press.

- [4] Aaker. (1992). The Value of Brand Equity. *Journal of business strategy*, 13(4), 27-32.
- [5] Aaker. (2015). *Managing Brand Equity*. New York: Simon & Schuster Inc.
- [6] Aaker., D. A., & Biel., A. L. (1993). *Brand equity & Advertising: advertising's role in building strong brands*. New Jersey: L. Erlbaum Associates.
- [7] Abba, J., & Hutchinson, J. (1987). Dimensions of Consumer Research. *Journal of Consumer Research*.
- [8] Agarwal, M., & Rao, V. (1996). An Empirical comparison of consumer based measures of brand Equity. *Marketing Letters*, 7(3), 237-247.
- [9] Alamro, A., & Rowley, J. (2011). Antecedents of Brand preference for mobile telecommunication services. *Journal of product & Brand management*, 20(6), 475-486.
- [10] Babbie, E. (2007). *The Basics of Social Research*. Cengage Learning.
- [11] Balaji, M. S. (2011). Building Strong Service Brands: The Hierarchical Relationship Between Brand Equity Dimensions. *IUP Journal of Brand Management*.
- [12] Baldauf, A., Cravens, K. S., & Binder, G. (2003). Performance consequences of brand equity management: Evidence from organizations in the value chain. *Journal of product and brand management*, 12(4), 220-236.
- [13] Barney, J. B. (1991). Firm Resources and Sustained competitive Advantage. *Journal of Management*, vol. 17, 99-120.
- [14] Bartlett, C. A., & Ghoshal, S. (1991). Global Strategic Management: Impact on the new frontiers of strategy research. *Strategic management Journal*, vol. 12, 5-16.
- [15] Bartlett, J., Kortlik, J., & Higgins, C. (2001). Determining appropriate Sample size for survey Research. *Information Technology, learning and performance Journal*, 43-50.
- [16] Bell, E., Bryman, A., & Harley, B. (2018). *Business Research Methods*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [17] Bello. (2007). Does an absence of Brand Equity Generalize across product classes. *Journal of Business Research*, 125-131.
- [18] Beneke, J., Sousa, S. D., Mbuyu, M., & Wickham, B. (2016). The effect of negative online customer reviews on brand equity and purchase intention of consumer of electronics in South africa. *The international review of retail, distribution and consumer research*, 26(2), 171-201.
- [19] Bernue's, A., Olaizola, A., & Corcoran, K. (2003). Extrinsic attributes of red meat as indicators of quality in Europe: an application for market segmentation. *Food quality and preference Journal*, 14(4), 265-276.
- [20] Bharadwaj, S. G., Varadarajan, P. R., & Fahy, J. (1993). Sustainable Competitive advantage in Service industries: A conceptual Model and Research Propositions. *Journal of Marketing*, 83-99.
- [21] Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2011). *Business Research Methods 3rd Ed*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- [22] Cannon, P. D. (1997). An examination of the Nature of Trust in Buyer-Seller Relationship. *Journal of Marketing*, 35-51.
- [23] Cathy, J., Cobb-Wagren, Cynthia, A., & Naveen, D. (1995). Brand Equity, Brand preference, and Purchase intent. *Journal of Advertising*, 25-40.
- [24] Chaudhuri, & Holbrook. (2001). The chain of Effects from Brand Trust and Brand Affect to Brand Performance: The Role of Brand Loyalty. *The Journal of Marketing*, 65(2), 81-93.
- [25] Chaudhuri, A., & Morris, B. H. (2001). The Chain of Effects From Brand Trust and Brand Performance: The Role of Brand Loyalty. *Journal of Marketing*, 65(2), 81-82.
- [26] Chung, K. K., Han, D., & Park, S. B. (2001). The effect of brand personality and brand identification on brand loyalty: Applying the theory of social identification. *Japanese psychological research*, 43 (4), 195-206.

- [27] Chung, S., & Park, J. (2015). The influence of brand personality and relative brand identification on brand loyalty in the European mobile phone market: Brand personality and relative brand identification. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 34(1), 10.
- [28] Connelly, B., Certo, S. T., Ireland, R. D., & Reutzel, C. R. (2011). Signaling Theory: A Review and Assessment. *Journal of Management*.
- [29] Cooper, D., & Schindler, P. (2013). *Business Research Methods 12th Ed.* New York: McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
- [30] Dawar, N., & Pillutla, M. M. (2000). Impact of product-harm crises on brand equity: The moderating role of consumer expectations. *Journal of Marketing*, 37(2), 215-226 .
- [31] De-Chernatony. (2011). *Creating Powerful Brands 4th Ed.* Oxfordshire: Taylor & Francis Group.
- [32] Delgado-Ballester, & Hernandez-Espallardo. (2008). Building online brands through brand alliances in internet. *European Journal of Marketing*.
- [33] Dodds, W. B., Monroe, K. B., & Grewal, D. (1991). Effect of price, brand and store information on buyers' product evaluation. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 28(3), 307-319.
- [34] Dunning, J. (1995). Reappraising the eclectic paradigm in an age of alliance capitalism. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 26(3), 461-491.
- [35] Ehrenberg, R. J. (2018). Evidence Concerning the Importance of perceived Brand differentiation. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 42-54.
- [36] Erdem, T., & Swait, J. (2004). Brand Credibility, Brand Consideration, and Choice. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 31(1), 191-198.
- [37] Fader, E. B. (2015). Stockpiling Points in Linear Loyalty Programs. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 253-267.
- [38] Fahy, J., & Hooley, G. (2000). The development and impact of marketing capabilities in Central Europe. *Journal of international business studies*, 31(1), 63-81.
- [39] Farris, Paul, W. W., Bendle, N. T., Pfeifer, P. E., & Reibstein, D. J. (2010). *Marketing Metrics: The Definitive Guide to Measuring Marketing Performance.* New Jersey: Pearson Education.
- [40] Finkle., C. (2018, October 5th). *What is Brand Association.* Retrieved from Brand Marketing Blog: <https://brandmarketingblog.com/articles/branding-definitions/brand-association/>
- [41] Fornell. (2016). Gauging the effect of Marketing intangible. *Journal of Marketing*, 92-107.
- [42] Gibbert, M. (2006). Generalizing about uniqueness: an essay on an apparent paradox in the resource-based view. *Journal of management inquiry*, 15(2), 124-134.
- [43] Guillaume, Balmer, & John. (1999). The ACID Test of Corporate Identity Management. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 15:69-92.
- [44] Herbig, P., & Milewicz, J. (1993). The relationship of reputation and credibility to brand success. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, vol 10(3).
- [45] Hoskisson, R. E. (1999). Theory and Research in strategic management: Swings of a pendulum. *Journal of management*, 25(3), 417-456.
- [46] Hyunjung., H. I., Seongseop., S. K., Elliot., S., & Han., H. (2012). Conceptualizing Destination Brand Equity Dimensions from a Consumer-Based Brand Equity Perspective. *Journal of travel & Tourism*, 29(4), 385-403.
- [47] Inkbot-design. (2019, 05 1st). *What is Brand Association? meaning & Examples of Associations.* Retrieved from Medium.com:<https://medium.com/@inkbotdesign/what-is-brand-association-meaning-examples-of-associations-19791284bb99>
- [48] Jobber, C. a. (2016). *Principles and Practice of Marketing.* New York: Mcgraw- Hill Education.

- [49] Joppe., M. (2000, December 16th). *The Research Process*. Retrieved from ryerson: <https://www.ryerson.ca/~mjoppe/rp.htm>
- [50] Kabura, E. (2002). *Usage of brand equity assets in positioning brands (the case of agrochemical industries based in Nairobi)*. Nairobi: university of Nairobi.
- [51] Kanyuiro, S. G. (2018). *Brand Equity and Loyalty Among Account Holders in Unaitas Sacco, Nairobi City County, Kenya*. Nairobi: Kenyatta University.
- [52] Kapferer, J. (2012). *The new strategic brand management: Advanced insights and strategic thinking (5th ed.)* . London: Kogan Page Publishers.
- [53] Karasek, R., & Bryant, P. (2012). Signalling Theory: Past, Present, and Future. *Academy of strategic management Journal*, 11(1), 91-99.
- [54] Kayaman, & Arasli, a. (2007). Customer based brand equity: Evidence from hotel industry. *Managing Service quality: an international Journal*, 92-109.
- [55] Kayaman., R., & Arasli., H. (2007). Customer based brand equity: evidence from the hotel industry. *An International Journal*, vol. 17, (1).
- [56] Keller, K. L. (1993). Conceptualizing, Measuring, and managing customer-based brand equity. *Journal of Marketing*, 57(7), 1-22.
- [57] Keller. (2008). *Strategic brand management: building, measuring, and managing brand equity (3rd ed.)*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
- [58] (2019). *Kenya Population and Housing Census Results*. Nairobi: Kenya National Bureau of Statistics.
- [59] Kim, M. K., Park, M. C., & Jeong, D. H. (2004). The effect of Customer Satisfaction and Switching Barrier on Customer Loyalty in Korean mobile telecommunication Services. *Telecommunication policy Journal*, 28(2), 145-159.
- [60] Kimpakorn, N., & Tocquer, G. (2010). Service Brand Equity and Employee Brand Commitment. *Journal of Service Marketing*, vol. 24 Issue 5.
- [61] Kirmani, A., & Rao, A. (2000). No pain, No gain: A critical review of the literature on signaling unobservable product quality. *Journal of Marketing*, 64(2), 66-79.
- [62] Kothari, C. R. (2012). *Research Methodology: Methods & techniques (2nd revised Ed)*. New Delhi: New Age International Publishers.
- [63] Kothari. (2003). *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques*. New Delhi: Pannerselvam.
- [64] Kothari., C. R. (2004). *Research Methodology: Methods and techniques 2nd Ed*. New Delhi: New Age International Publishers.
- [65] Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). *Marketing Management 15th. Ed*. London: pearson.
- [66] Leon., A. C., Davis., L. L., & Kraemer, H. C. (2011). The role and interpretation of pilot studies in clinical research. *J Psychiatr*, 45(5), 626-629.
- [67] Manternach, L. (2011). Does your brand have top of mind awareness? *Corridor Business Journal*, 7(52), 26.
- [68] McLeod., S. A. (2019). *Sampling Method*. Retrieved from SimplyPsychology: <https://www.simplypsychology.org/sampling.html>
- [69] Munyao., K. P. (2017). *Role of customer based brand equity on brand market performance in the banking service sector in Kenya. PhD Thesis. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology*.
- [70] Newbert, S. L. (2007). Empirical Research on the resource- based view of the firm:An assessment and suggestionsfor future research. *Strategic Management Journal*, vol. 28, 124-146.

- [71] Nyagechi., M. (2011). *Perception of brand equity of daily newspapers by media buying agencies in Nairobi, Kenya*. Nairobi: University of Nairobi.
- [72] Odera., E. (2015). *Factors influencing loyalty towards paint brands by contractors in Nairobi City County*. Nairobi: University Of Nairobi.
- [73] Oliva, T. A., Oliver, R. L., & MacMillan, I. (1992). A catastrophe model for developing service satisfaction strategies. *Journal of Marketing*, vol. 56, 83-95.
- [74] Omamo, F. (2011). *Factors influencing brand loyalty among consumers of Mumias, Muhoroni, Sony and Chemelil Sugar brands in Kisumu County*. Nairobi: University Of Nairobi.
- [75] Ovidiu. (2010). The Relationship Between The Dimensions of Brand Loyalty. An Empirical Investigation Among Romanian Urban Consumers. *Management and Marketing Journal*, vol. 5(4).
- [76] Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V., & Berry, L. (1988). SERVQUAL: A Multiple-Item Scale for Measuring Consumer Perceptions of Service Quality. *Journal of Retailing*, vol. 6 no. 1.
- [77] Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V., & Berry, L. (1996). The behavioral Consequences of Service Quality. *Journal of Marketing*, vol. 60, No. 2, 31-46.
- [78] Parasuraman., A., & Zeithaml., V. A. (1988). SERVQUAL: A Multiple-Item Scale for Measuring Consumer Perceptions of Service Quality. *Journal of Retailing*, 64(1).
- [79] Penrose, E. T. (2009). *The theory of the growth of the firm*. New York: OXFORD University Press.
- [80] Percy, L., & Rossiter, J. (1992). A Model of Brand Awareness and Brand Attitude Advertising Strategies. *Psychology and Marketing*, 7(4), 263-274.
- [81] Quan, T. H. (2006). *Retailers' perceptions of product brand equity: An empirical study of Vietnamese independent grocers*. Lismore: Southern Cross University.
- [82] Rao, P. (2016). A study on Consumer Perception towards E-Shopping. *international Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 26-35.
- [83] Rossiter, J. R., & Percy, L. (1987). *Advertising and Promotion Management*. Singapore: McGraw-Hill.
- [84] Rumelt, R., Schendel, D., & Teece, D. (1995). Fundamental issues in strategy: A research agenda. *Rutgers University press*.
- [85] Sarndal., C. E., Swensson., B., & Wretman, B. (2003). Model assisted survey sampling: springer Series in Statistics.
- [86] Sheskin., D. J. (2007). *Handbook of parametric and Nonparametric Statistical Procedures*. Chapman & Hall.
- [87] Shona, M. (2019, may 15). *Descriptive Research*. Retrieved from Scribbr: <https://scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>
- [88] Srivastava, R., & Shocker, A. D. (1991). Brand Equity: A perspective on its meaning and measurement. *Marketing Science Institute*.
- [89] Steenkamp. (1997). The increasing power of store brands: Building loyalty and market share. *Journal of marketing research*, 30(6) 917-930.
- [90] Suoranta, M., Mattila, M., & Munnukka, J. (2005). Technology-based services: a study on the drivers and inhibitors of mobile banking. *International Journal of Management and Decision Making* , 6(1), 33-46.
- [91] Teijlingen., V. E., Rennie., A. M., Hundley., V., & Graham., W. (2001). The importance of conducting and reporting pilot studies: the example of the Scottish Births Survey. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, vol. 34, 289-295.
- [92] Thompson, W. F., Amponsah, D., & Mosley, G. (2017). Mobile phones Services in Sub Saharan Africa: A model for researching Customer Loyalty. *proceedings of the Association of Collegiate Marketing Educators* (p. 43). Texas: ACME Proceedings.

- [93] Tokuda, A. (2005). The Critical Assessment of the Resource-Based View of Strategic Management: The Source of Heterogeneity of the firm. *Ritsumeikan International Affairs*, vol. 3, 125-150.
- [94] Vuong., Q.-H., Napier., N. K., Ho., T. M., Nguyen., V. H., Vuong., T. T., Pham., H. H., & Nguyen, H. K. (2018). Effects of work environment and collaboration on research productivity in Vietnamese social Sciences: evidence from 2008 to 2017. *scopus data, studies in Higher Education*, 44(12), 2132-2147.
- [95] Wainer., H., & Braun., H. I. (1998). Test Validity. *Hilldale*.
- [96] Wernerfelt, B. (1984). A resource-based view of the firm. *Strategic management Journal*, 5(2), 171-180.
- [97] Zeithaml, V. A., & Bitner, M. J. (2003). *Services Marketing: Integrating Customer Focus across the Firm. 3rd Ed.* New York: McGraw-Hill.
- [98] Zeithaml. (1988). Consumer Perceptions of price, Quality, and Value: A Means-End Model and Synthesis of Evidence. *Journal of Marketing*, 52(3), 2-22.